

MODERN METHODS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. *The 21st century is the century of science and progress, the age of scientific technology, and it's not just called that. Everything around us is rapidly changing and developing, and teaching and learning technologies are not lagging behind either. What is meant by teaching and learning technologies? What are the differences between method, tool, and technique? And why is it better to use modern ones than traditional ones? This work accurately demonstrates interpretations of all these terms and reveals some effective ways of teaching foreign languages.*

Keywords: *teaching methods, foreign language, traditional teaching, modern teaching, teaching tool, teaching technique.*

Being residents of this century, we are all dependent on new technologies. It undoubtedly effects on every sphere as well as the sphere of education. So it can be argued that modern methods of teaching and learning are more effective than traditional ones, being developed with innovations. This work explores the core of modern methods of foreign language teaching, compares them with traditional, established methods through the generations, and describes the main aspects of its essence.

The essence of teaching

According to Munna (2021) “It is a teacher responsibility to ensure regular interaction occurs between the basic human capabilities of a learner and the culturally invented technologies so that it finally leads to enhancement in their cognitive capabilities” (p. 2). As Biesta (2023) wrote in his book: “the word ‘teaching’ comes from the Old English word ‘tæcan’. Tæcan carries such meanings as ‘to show,’ ‘to point out,’ to instruct,’ ‘to warn’ and ‘to persuade,’ ‘sign’ or ‘mark’” (p. 257). This leads to the conclusion that teaching is about “providing signs” or the “outward expression of what one knows”, as Hansen (1995, p. 1) has put it. This idea is echoed in Stenhouse’s observation that “teachers express, in a form accessible to learners, an understanding of the nature of what is to be learned” (1988, p. 46). “Teaching is an act of providing content to students”, “teaching is about providing access to skills or attitudes or dispositions”, “teaching is not a matter of the transportation of something from teacher to student, but rather is about teachers seeking to evoke a response from their students through their teaching. This is teaching that asks something from students, so to speak, rather than teaching as giving something to students,” he says. (p. 257)

Teaching Methods

“Method is an organized, orderly, systematic, and well-planned procedure aimed at facilitating and enhancing students’ learning. It is undertaken according to some rules, which are usually psychological. That is, it considers primarily the abilities, needs, and interests of the learners. Method is employed to achieve certain specific aims of instruction” (Hasanova et.al)

The method should be distinguished from other aspects of teaching:

Sam, 2020)

Teaching methods are divided into two: teacher-centered and student-centered approaches. First one (deductive) conceptualizes the teacher in the learning process as a key figure, while the alternative (inductive) regards both a teacher and a student as two complementary agents.

Traditional Methods vs. Modern

Alessa & Hussein (2023) clarify:

Traditional Methods: known as conventional education, ‘the old way of teaching’. This is the deductive method, where the teacher, standing at the blackboard and writing down the material, imparts knowledge to the class and students just “memorize and recite the information given, take in the decisions made by the teacher” (p. 69). This all leads to students’ “lack of decision-making and problem-solving skills” (p. 69). They only want to get good marks on exams, and they were not taught to learn for themselves (Perse, 2017).

Modern Teaching Methods: “Education reforms mean that learning is taught from a completely different angle. Progressive educational practices focus more on the individual student’s needs rather than assuming all students are at the same level of understanding. The modern way of teaching is more activity-based, using questioning, explaining, demonstration, and collaboration techniques. Modern learning encourages students to collaborate and therefore be more productive” (Jackson, 2017).

Living in the 21st century, it is impossible not to succumb to the influence of technology. And, of course, with the introduction of technology into the education system, it will change and reveal all new methods that have a completely different view and approach to the teaching and learning system. Teachers treat each student as a person and take their needs fully into account. They try to make the learning process much more active. The methods are based on actions that fully involve students in the learning process, which helps them improve their skills to cope with any difficulties in the future, and the teacher only guides and helps them achieve their goals. (Mehta, 2019) and (Gray, 2019).

Foreign language teaching

There are so many views and opinions on how the information intake should be carried out. But in fact, all of them are successful together or in proper use. Moeller & Catalano, in their work ‘Foreign Language Teaching and Learning’, discuss:

If a language is studied in a small community, not being the main language spoken in the society where it is taught, then it can be called ‘foreign’. To “communicate effectively and

creatively and to participate in real-life situations through the language of the authentic culture itself,” individuals must learn a language. Language scholars have 2 terms: acquisition - the process of learning first and second languages naturally, and learning - the formal, in-classroom settings. Conventionally, this process is thought to be a ‘mimetic’ activity, with repeating or imitating new information. In 1959, Noam Chomsky’s (1959) review of B.F. Skinner’s (1957) Verbal Behavior presented another perspective: “language was a rule-governed activity, not a set of habits” (p. 327). Long (1985) advocated that “language input was made comprehensible by simplifying the input, by using linguistic and extralinguistic cues, and by modifying the interactional structure of the conversation”, that “learners, to acquire language, cannot simply listen to input, rather they must be active co-constructive participants who interact and negotiate the type of input they receive” (Moeller & Catalano, p. 327). Then researchers discovered nine contemporary language learning theories: Universal Grammar, Autonomous Induction, Associative-Cognitive CREED, Skill Acquisition, Input Processing, Processability, Concept-Oriented Approach, Interaction Framework, and Vygotskian Sociocultural Theory (VanPatten and Williams, 2008). But the most common is the Socio-cultural Theory (SCT) urged by Vygotsky: “participation in culturally organized activities is essential for learning to occur” (p. 328)

Here are some methods adopted by Rashov (2024) in their research:

“1. Observational Studies: Classroom observations were conducted to analyze the implementation of various teaching methods, focusing on student engagement, interaction, and language use in real-time.

2. Surveys and Questionnaires: Pre and post-intervention surveys were distributed to students and teachers to gather qualitative and quantitative data on their experiences, preferences, and perceived effectiveness of different teaching methods.

3. Interviews: Semi-structured interviews with educators provided insights into their experiences with modern teaching methodologies, challenges faced, and perceived student outcomes.

4. Action Research: Teachers implemented specific teaching strategies (e.g., TBLT, CLIL) in their classrooms, collecting data on student performance and engagement over time to assess the impact of these methods.” (p. 162)

Conclusion

Overall, teaching is not only about providing the information, but also about assurance that learners comprehended the information clearly and have the ability to use it. To achieve this goal, instructors use a variety of methods, which include the usage of different tools and techniques, trying to focus more on contemporary ones, increasingly used currently, more understandable, and beneficial for today’s society. As old-fashioned strategies do not provide the opportunities for developing decision-making and problem-solving skills, in today’s world is key to success. Lately, there have been discovered several systems of effectively teaching, but there is always an own way of taking advantage of each.

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